

Enhancing the Value of Fundamental Duties through Indian Constitution

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Abstract

In fact, fundamental rights of the constitution always find favour with everybody concerned. But fundamental duties only scarcely get the attention even of the citizens of the country for whom they are basically meant. One very strong reason for that is the fact that fundamental rights receive constitutional protection in the constitution itself for which Articles 32 and 226 have been created in which through the instrumentality of writs our fundamental rights are judicially accorded protection by High Courts and Supreme Court of our country. But in the case of fundamental duties no such legal or judicial protection has been bestowed upon in Indian Constitution. But gradually our apex judiciary is treating fundamental duties alongside directive principal to be fundamental in the constitutional governance of the country. A comparison has been expressly made between the position of fundamental duties given under different countries of the world so that the relative reality of different constitutions on the subject of fundamental duties may be presented clearly in the present paper.

Keywords: Fundamental Right, Fundamental Duty, Constitutional Governance, Writs.

Introductory : Meaning & Value of Duties

In today's increasingly 'rights conscious mind set', 'duty consciousness of the people' diminished to the serious levels. Experience sufficiently shows that duty conscious people tend to make society more peace-loving and conciliatory rather than to be more dispute-prone and litigational. Celebrated sociologist Duguit remarkably say, "Nobody possesses any right except the right of always doing his duty." India's pious book Geeta assuringly avers, "Your Right lies in performing your Duty and not in seeking the fruits there of." Thus, Duty – abiding habits of the people would mean and ensure not only the welfare of others but also one's own welfare. Hindu culture has known the duty concept right from the beginning. Hindu system stands for 'duty'.

The Dharmashastras laid down the duties of the king in minute details. His foremost duty was to uphold the law. Likewise, Dharmashastra deals with the duties of the individuals in all walks of life P.V. Kane, in his famous work 'History of Dharmashastra', says, "suppression of wrath, truthfulness of speech, Justice, forgiveness, begetting of children upon one's own wedded wife, purity of conduct, avoidance of quarrel, simplicity, and maintenance of dependent are considered to be duties belonging to all."⁽¹⁾

Fundamental Duties Under International law

United Nations General Assembly adopted 'The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948'. Unanimously in which individuals of the world have been enjoined about their 'duties' to the community in which alone the free and full development of his personality is possible. The fundamental duties under Article 51A have been created in consonance with the spirit manifested in this Universal Declaration.

Fundamental Duties & Indian Constitution

Unfortunately, market culture of today have made people more self-seeking individuals rather than to be more duty-loving performers. The fate of the country cannot be better if its citizens are not sufficiently harnessed towards duty-fulfillment. Here, this would be pertinent to mention of the fundamental duties of Indian People which have been enshrined in Article 51A of constitution. The rights have been comprehensively contemplated including everything that is important for citizens to follow in their normal course of life so that general awareness towards Duty-consciousness and Duty-fulfillment is ensured. Following is the enumeration of different fundamental duties which find place in part IV A & Article 51A of Indian constitution: ⁽²⁾

“It shall be the duty of every citizen of India :

- (a) to abide by the constitution and respect its ideals and institution, the national flag and the national Anthem;
- (b) to cherish and follow the noble ideals which inspired our national struggle for freedom;
- (c) to uphold and protect the sovereignty, unity and integrity of India;
- (d) to defend the country & render national service when called upon to do so;
- (e) to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities; **to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women;**
- (f) to value and preserve the rich heritage of our composite culture;
- (g) to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life, and to have compassion for living creatures;
- (h) to develop the scientific temper, humanism and the spirit of inquiry and reform;
- (i) to safe guard public property and to abjure violence;
- (j) to strive towards excellence in all spheres of individual and collective activity so that the nation constantly rises to higher levels of endeavors and achievement;
- (k) who is parent or guardian to provide opportunities for education to his child or, as the case, ward between the age of six and fourteen years.

As to the enforceability of these duties, our constitution is silent. Fundamental rights are specifically made enforceable but the Directive Principles of State Policy are not enforceable by a Court of Law. As regards enforceability of fundamental duties nothing is stated. But over the years it came to be interpreted that these duties are judicially enforceable. Whenever and wherever, they are found essential ‘as fundamental’ in the democratic governance of the country by the apex judiciary.

Dynamic Interpretation of These Fundamental Duties

As we see that these fundamental duties are sacrosanct and sacred enough at the core, but at the same time these are not justiciable; meaning thereby that they have not been specifically made enforceable by our constitution.

As per the author of this paper, the legislative drafting of Article 51A speaks of multi-dimensional approach with which these fundamental duties have been crafted. One by one we will see, what is implied in the language of these duties. Like we see in Article 51A –

- (a) Abiding by the Constitutional governance including respect for National Flag and National Anthem;
- (b) Cherishing ideals of National Movement for Country’s Independence;
- (c) Upholding all the ingredients of a powerful and strong nation as manifested through political sovereignty and always protecting the cause of unity and integrity of Indian nation;
- (d) Always being ready for urgent national service, like the one that of National Disaster Management whenever called upon to do so by the citizens of India;
- (e) Promoting the harmonious brotherly spirit and relationship across all sections of Indian people and specifically and consciously renounce all the practices downgrading the dignity of women (rather, in other words, this is indirectly helping the cause of Women Empowerment);
- (f) Always striving to preserve the spontaneous composite culture of Indian people which is so natural to us and that’s our proud heritage.
- (g) Having concern for the cause of natural environment, including all its biotic and abiotic components and having religious and pious compassion for all living creatures;
- (h) This fundamental duty is devoted to the development of scientific spirit in each individual and the feeling for all humanity, and the spirit of discovery and also making efforts for bringing about reformation in any part of national life;
- (i) Never to sabotage public property and always to avoid and evade any kind of violent acts;
- (j) Further to go on working hard for successive acts towards excellence achievement in all endeavours – collective or individual, in order that the process of nation-building always advance ahead unhurdled and ceaselessly.
- (k) This eleventh fundamental duty is about ensuring the Right to Education through casting this obligation on every parent or guardian to provide education for his ward who is between the age of six and fourteen years.

Position of Fundamental Duties in Different Countries

As per western jurisprudence, the concept of rights and duties go together. If 'A' has a definite right, there is a corresponding duty on someone else relating to that 'right'.

The inclusion of a chapter on 'fundamental duties', our constitution has accepted the concept of, 'unenumerated rights' as per the legal co-relationship of right's, to put it simply.

However, most of the western countries like Britain, Canada, France and America do not contain Duties of the citizens, but it does not mean that the people of their countries do not follow any duty rather they have a sense of responsibility in terms of patriotism and duty-fulfillment as a result of education and training in the basic duties and obligations of citizenship.

As far as socialist countries are concerned their constitutions prominently place great emphasis on basic duties of the citizen. The then Soviet constitution contained a comprehensive chapter on the citizen's duties stressing on observing all the standard of socialist conduct.

Yugoslavian Constitution has laid down "the freedom and right shall be achieved in solidarity among the people by the fulfillment of their duties towards each other." The constitution of the republic of China lays down specific duties of the people. China's constitution also lays down, "Citizens of China have the right to work, that is, the right to guaranteed employment and payment for the work accordance with its quantity and quality." This is to be submitted that the right to work should also be guaranteed to every Indian citizens who are expected to fulfill certain duties to the Nation as a poor and unemployed person cannot reasonably be expected to observe his duties towards the society. Another Asian country Japan incorporates a number of basic duties in its constitution almost more than thirty five nations of the world contain specific provision on fundamental duties in their national laws.

Legal Utility and Appraisal of Fundamental Duties

These fundamental duties of the citizens have been inserted by the 42nd Amendment Act, 1976 in our constitution.⁽³⁾ The Constitution of some countries also provide for the duties of the state, namely – (a) protect youth against exploitation and moral, intellectual and physical abandonment; (b) organise public education; (c) to protect family (d) to ensure health, protection material security to all; (e) to create welfare agencies for physically and abandoned children; (f) to profit labour; (g) to create conditions necessary to make the right to work an effective one. In regard to the duties of the state, it is submitted that in a country like ours where poverty is in abundance, it should be the minimum fundamental duty of the state to ensure that no one is ill-fed, ill-clad and ill-housed.

These Fundamental Rights are eleven commandments – morally and ethically binding on us. If real socio-economic transformation has to take place, the emphasis has to be on the duties of both citizen as well as the state. In order to make an affluent India, both intense education for the positive and proactive performance of constitutional duties is a must. In Hindu jurisprudence, co-relative of duty is not right but duty.

In the last, stressing on the relevance of the fundamental duties, R.C. Lahoti, J. in AIIMS Students' Union vs. AIIMS,⁽⁴⁾ observed, "Fundamental duties as defined in Article 51-A, are not made enforceable by a writ of court just as the fundamental rights are, but it cannot be lost sight of that 'duties' in Part IV A. Hence, though Article 51-A does not expressly cast any fundamental duty on the State, the fact remains that the duty of every citizen of India is the collective duty of (the) state."

References

1. P.V. Kane, "History of Dharmashastra".
2. Article 51-A of The Constitution of India.
3. 42nd Amendment Act, 1976
4. AIR 2001 SC at 3280

